

Supplementary File 4. Evaluation criteria of each item for assessment of certainty of evidence

Items	Evaluation criteria
Risk of bias	The risk of bias in the individual studies was evaluated as described in Materials and Methods. Based on the results, this was scored at three levels: low risk of bias (0), moderate risk of bias (−1), and high risk of bias (−2). If the risk of bias in individual studies was different between studies, the worst assessment was used.
Indirectness	Two reviewers independently investigate whether included studies conform to PICOS or PECOS (indirectness). Indirectness is evaluated on a two-level scale for each item, with "−" if it is indirect and "+" if it is not indirect. Based on the total number of (−), the indirectness was judged as follows: 0, low in-directness (0); 1, moderate indirectness (−1); and 2–5, high indirectness (−2). If the indireciness was different between studies, the worst assessment was used.
Imprecision	Imprecision was evaluated based on the total sample sizes of the included studies. Based on the total sample size, we judged this as: >100, precise (0); 40–99, moderately imprecise (−1); and <39, highly imprecise (−2).
Inconsistency	Inconsistencies were evaluated using I^2 values calculated from the forest plots. This was judged at three levels: 0%–40%, low inconsistency (0); 41%–70%, moderate inconsistency (−1); and 71%–100%, high inconsistency (−2).
Publication bias	Publication bias was evaluated by visual inspection of funnel plots. This was judged at three levels: low publication bias (0), moderate publication bias (−1), and high publication bias (−2). The reporting bias is basically assessed using the results of the funnel plot mentioned above. However, if there are more unpublished studies than the number of included studies, the assessment is downgraded by −1. If the result of the funnel plot is "high reporting bias (−2)," the result is unchanged.